

THE IMPACT OF SOMATIC DISEASES OF PREGNANT WOMEN ON THE HEALTH OF THE NEWBORN

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Abstract: The article presents information on the impact of inflammatory and somatic diseases of pregnant women on the health of the mother during and after childbirth, as well as the condition of the newborn

Keywords: extragenital pathology, pregnancy, fetus, infection, normotrophy, hypotrophy.

Purpose of the study: Evaluation of the impact of somatic diseases of pregnant women on the health of the newborn.

Materials and methods of research: The screening study included pregnant women registered for pregnancy at the Tashkent family clinic with inflammatory diseases of the urinary system and associated clinical conditions. The total number of pregnant women with this pathology was 409 pregnant women. Pregnant women with a pregnancy period of 8-12 weeks were selected for participation in the study. The average age of pregnant women in the first group was 27.5 ± 0.93 years, the average body mass index (BMI) was 18.0 ± 0.48 . In the second group, the average age of pregnant women was 27.2 ± 0.87 , and BMI was 22.0 ± 1.58 . Based on the obtained data, all pregnant women were divided into two groups, so the 1st group of pregnant women with infectious diseases of the urinary tract (exacerbation of chronic pyelonephritis, gestational pyelonephritis, asymptomatic bacteriuria) was 241 (58.9%), the 2nd group - pregnant women with extragenital pathology - 168 (41%) women. Mathematical processing of all the results obtained during the study was performed by methods of variation statistics.

Research results: In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the problem of perinatal nephropathy, since many kidney diseases in older children and adults originate in the ante- and perinatal periods. Any pathological stress effect on the fetus and newborn affects the kidneys. The increase in urinary

system diseases in newborns is associated with an increase in the frequency of congenital and hereditary forms caused by disorders in the mother-placenta-fetus system.

There is no doubt that renal pathology in pregnant women affects the condition of the fetus. Among newborns born to women with azotemia, the mortality rate is five times higher than in children born to healthy mothers. Gestational pyelonephritis, like exacerbation of chronic pyelonephritis, is accompanied by inflammatory changes in the placenta, intrauterine infection, as well as hypoxic and toxic lesions of the fetal kidneys. An additional threat to the future child is the prescription of antibiotics and other drugs during pregnancy, especially with polypharmacy. Analysis of the clinical condition of newborns showed that perinatal mortality in the first group was 3.3% (n = 8), while in the second group this figure was lower - 1.2% (n = 2) (Fig. 1).

Note: *p<0.05 reliability of differences between groups
Group 1: pregnant women with uterine fibroids pathology;
2- group of pregnant women with somatic pathology

Fig. 1. Analysis of perinatal mortality, %

Perinatal mortality of newborns was analyzed depending on the clinical variants of kidney disease (Fig. 2).

P-

chronic pyelonephritis, HP-gestational pyelonephritis, BB-asymptomatic bacteriuria

Note: *p<0.05 reliability of differences between groups

Fig. 2. Analysis of perinatal mortality in various clinical variants of kidney disease, %

In the first group, 233 children were born (96.6%), and the mortality rate was 8 cases (3.3%). In the second group, 166 children were born (98.8%), of which 2 (1.2%) died. Analysis of the clinical condition of the newborns showed that among the patients of the first group, 18.4% (n=43) had normotrophy, 25.3% (n=59) had mild hypotrophy, 25% (n=58) had moderate hypotrophy, and 31% (n=73) had severe hypotrophy. In the second group, the indicators were distributed as follows: 37% (n=62) with normotrophy, 23.5% (n=39) with mild hypotrophy, 28% (n=46) with moderate hypotrophy, and 11.4% (n=19) with severe hypotrophy (Fig. 4.7).

Note: ** $p < 0.01$ reliability of differences between groups

Fig. 3. Analysis of perinatal mortality in various clinical variants of kidney disease, %

Comparison of the studied parameters between the groups revealed significant differences. The second group had 44% more newborns with normotrophy ($p < 0.01$) compared to the first. At the same time, in the first group the number of children with severe hypotrophy was 26% higher ($p < 0.01$) than in the second.

Table 1. Results of the confidence interval (CI) analysis

Category	1st group (%)	CI 1st group (lower upper limit)	1st - 2nd	2nd group (%)	CI 2nd group (lower upper limit)	2nd - 1st	Statistical significance of differences
Normotrophy	18.4	13.5 - 23.3	-	37.0	29.7 - 44.3	-	<0.01
Hypotrophy of the CT	25.0	19.5 - 30.5	-	28.0	21.2 - 34.8	-	
Hypotrophy of the LS	25.3	19.8 - 30.8	-	23.5	17.0 - 29.9	-	
Hypotrophy of the TS	31.0	25.2 - 36.8	-	11.4	6.6 - 16.2	-	<0.01

As can be seen from the presented data (Table 1), the second group has a significantly higher percentage of normotrophy (37.0%) compared to the first group (18.4%). Confidence intervals do not overlap (13.5 - 23.3 in the first group and 29.7 - 44.3 in the second), which indicates a statistically significant difference between the groups. In the first group, the percentage of children with severe hypotrophy (31.0%) is significantly higher than in the second (11.4%). Confidence intervals do not overlap (25.2 - 36.8 in the first group and 6.6 - 16.2 in the second), which also indicates a statistically significant difference.

The percentage of children with moderate hypotrophy in the second group (28.0%) is slightly higher than in the first (25.0%). However, their confidence intervals (19.5-30.5 and 21.2-34.8) overlap, indicating that the differences are not statistically significant. For mild hypotrophy of the LS, the values in both groups are similar (25.3% in the first group and 23.5% in the second), and their

confidence intervals (19.8–30.8 and 17.0–29.9) overlap, also indicating that there is no statistically significant difference.

Conclusion: Normotrophy and severe hypotrophy (NS) have statistically significant differences between the groups. This confirms that in the second group there are significantly more children with normotrophy, and in the first group - with severe hypotrophy. Moderate (MS) and mild (LS) degrees of hypotrophy do not have reliable differences between the groups. The obtained results demonstrate that the conditions within the second group contribute to better fetal development (more normotrophy), while in the first group there is a higher frequency of severe hypotrophy.

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